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Executive Summary

This document corresponds to the Requirements Baseline (RB) deliverable of the CLIM4cities project, which aims to pioneer the development of Machine Learning (ML) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) models designed to downscale air and land surface temperature predictions in urban areas by a factor of at least ten. This initiative serves as a preliminary step towards the implementation of cost-effective Integrated Urban Climate and Weather components into local Digital Twin Systems. The RB analysis is the result of the WP1000 – Problem Formulation activities, and it includes the conclusions derived from the WP1100 – State-of-the-Art and Gap Analysis, WP1200 – Scientific, Technical and User Requirements, and WP1300 – EO Use Case Definition and ECV Description [Land Surface Temperature (LST) and Air Temperature 2m above ground (T2m)].

The **State-of-the-Art and Gap Analysis** shows the relevance of urban adaptation to climate change, as temperature extremes and urbanisation trends support the need to measure and predict urban climate parameters. In particular, the Urban Heat Island (UHI) effect is a physically well-known phenomenon, stemming from the warming of, first, the urban surfaces and, secondly, the air close to the ground through radiation from the urban stock. Research on this topic has matured within the last couple of decades, driven in part by the interest from the scientific community, but also due to the increased awareness of decision-makers and society at large regarding climate change and urbanisation trends and the multiple negative health effects associated with living in excessively warm conditions. Furthermore, there is huge potential in combining Earth Observation (EO) imagery with local crowdsourced citizen-owned weather station data, showing that there is a sufficiently large number of observations available to derive reliable quality assessment metrics, and consistent results modelling. The State-of-the-Art Gap Analysis conclusions, however, point out that consistently monitoring the urban heat exposure and the UHI effect is still, in this present-day, a complex spatio-temporal challenge. While the usage of deterministic physical models allows such inference, modelling urban climate and UHI at

relevant (sub-kilometric) spatial scales requires large computational power and huge amounts of input data, which hinders the ability of the local public sector in adopting such tools for operational forecast and/or monitoring purposes. On the other hand, ML and AI methods are becoming more attractive alternatives for local-scale post-processing of weather forecasts and climate projections, considering that they show comparable accuracy metrics, but significantly lower computational demand. Hence, the combination of crowdsourced data together with EO and such methods offers a promising road ahead for the uptake of EO in downscaling numerical weather predictions and climate projections, overcoming current limitations to achieve mature technical results. Such predictions can then be used to build operational urban climate services to help decision makers in short-term actions and long-term planning, and inform the citizens regarding their relative exposure to temperature-dependent risks. Nonetheless, while all these data sources have relevant information, their integration within a user-driven tool is still seemingly difficult, especially in terms of consolidating which requirements and features are most needed.

Hence, in the scope of the **Scientific, Technical and User Requirements**, CLIM4cities sought to engage with citizens, city planners and local stakeholders to evaluate their needs and priorities. On the other hand, there are scientific and technical aspects that need to be considered in order to develop a solution that complies with expected accuracy and reliability standards, as well as minimises the maintenance effort and cost of keeping the resulting air and land surface temperature models operational. As a result, this section describes the requirements that have been mapped from the users, technical and scientific perspectives. The user engagement workshops and dialogues clearly manifest a demand for better high-resolution UHI models, and demonstrate a mature environment able to utilise such data in relevant planning and operations if provided. The technical requirement analysis shows that it is possible to develop models that meet the user requirements, and outlines the scientific challenges that have to be overcome in order to do so.

Finally, the **EO Use Case Definition and ECV Description [LST and T2m]** summarises what Key Performance Indicators (KPI) have to be attained. Based on preliminary data collection and exploratory data analysis, along with pre-existing knowledge regarding local climate as well as the methods to be employed, the **CLIM4cities** models are expected to be confidently developed and validated, and easily transferable between locations, as the analysis shows that there are no significant climatic differences between the investigated cities. The KPIs further support the confidence of the consortium in achieving a robust modelling framework and reliable results, fit for the purpose of the engaged users.

1 Problem Formulation [WP1000]

1.1 State-of-the-Art and Gap Analysis [WP1100]

1.1.1 State of the Art

The rapid growth of urban populations has drawn attention to the pressing sustainability challenges that cities are facing (Bulkeley, 2013; Easterling et al., 2000). Among other environmental aspects, air temperature is a key climate variable on determining local environmental health, affecting directly and indirectly human life and ecosystems (Babcock et al., 2019; EEA, 2012). With climate change effects becoming increasingly evident, global focus has shifted in recent decades toward implementing adaptation strategies tailored to specific localities (EEA, 2006; Hallegatte and Corfee-Morlot, 2011). These strategies are particularly pertinent in areas experiencing heightened occurrences of extreme heat events.

Within this context of drivers, urban climate research aims to disclose the disturbances in air temperature caused by urbanisation, echoing the work of Luke Howard in "The Climate of London" (Alexander and Mills, 2014). Nowadays, such research has gained significant attention, driven by the escalating health impacts of extreme air temperature events linked to climate change. Consequently, there has been an exponential increase in the number of studies and publications focused on measuring UHI intensity. Despite this surge, a notable disparity exists; while approximately a quarter of these publications reference LST in their titles or abstracts, only 5% mention the energy balance components (i.e., interactions and exchanges of energy between urban environment, including building stock, air, and other components, these interactions can determine how energy can be absorbed, stored and released, and how can have an impact in the UHI effect; see Figure 1). This discrepancy often leads to incomplete assessments or erroneous conclusions, particularly regarding the disparities in daily temperature cycles between the surface and the lower atmosphere, such as those observed between surface and canopy layer UHI effects.

Figure 1 Bibliometric assessment of Urban Heat Island publications – annual number of publications mentioning each of three keyword search terms in their title and/or abstract: (i) Urban Heat Island (UHI); (ii) UHI and Land Surface Temperature; and (iii) UHI and Energy Balance. Data was retrieved from the Dimensions database (“Dimensions”, n.d.).

When addressing urban climate dynamics, the scarcity of cities equipped with extensive high-density mesoscale weather networks is a notable limitation (Chapman et al., 2017; De Vos et al., 2019). Consequently, despite understanding that urban development affects local near-surface air temperatures across various climatic contexts, accurately quantifying this impact remains challenging. The identification of the UHI phenomenon traces back to Luke Howard, who observed elevated air temperatures in London’s city centre compared to its rural outskirts (Howard, 1833). Subsequently, William Lowry (Lowry, 1977) introduced a conceptual framework elucidating how climate variables are influenced by three primary factors:

- the ‘background’ regional climate (e.g., Mediterranean Climate),
- the effects of local landscape (e.g., topography, coastal proximity), and
- the effects of local urbanisation (e.g., imperviousness, compactness).

Over the years, research has predominantly focused on understanding the impact of different urban typologies on local air temperatures and their repercussions on the local energy balance (Oke, 1988, 1987). Although urban climate studies have proliferated, particularly concerning near-surface atmospheric conditions, it is crucial to recognise that the UHI phenomenon is multifaceted and operates across various vertical levels; see Figure 2 (Oke et al., 2017). At the highest level, the Urban Boundary Layer (UBL) denotes the portion of the Atmospheric Boundary Layer (ABL) influenced by urban presence (Oke et al., 2017). While the ABL encompasses the lowest part of the atmosphere in contact with the surface – extending from 100 to 3000 metres, including the capping inversion and the overlying free atmosphere – the UBL's extent is typically determined by regional wind patterns. Consequently, under calm conditions, the urban influence manifests as a contained dome, whereas during significant regional wind events, an urban plume develops, dispersing city-related effects (e.g., pollutants) downwind (Oke et al., 2017). At this level, the Urban Heat Island Urban Boundary Layer (UHIUBL) represents the urban-rural air temperature difference above the height of urban structures (up to the UBL boundary). Measurement of UHIUBL can be conducted directly through aircraft sensors, balloons, or tall towers, or indirectly using LIDAR or RASS profilers (Oke et al., 2017).

Figure 2 Schematic illustration of the processes of and influencing urban climate and the urban heat island effect. Source: DWD (https://www.dwd.de/EN/research/climateenvironment/climate_impact/urbanism/urban_heat_island/urbanheatisland_node.html)

Generally, in urban climate studies, the Urban Canopy Layer (UCL) is the focal point when discussing the UHI effect (Oke et al., 2017). The UCL constitutes the lower segment of the urban atmosphere, sandwiched between ground surfaces and the average building heights. This stratum is where humans reside vertically, experiencing direct changes in air temperature, making it crucial for evaluating heat exposure. The UHI's magnitude is usually assessed by comparing air temperature data from a reference non-urban weather station with readings obtained either from fixed urban sensors or via mobile measurements conducted at approximately 2 to 3 metres above ground level (Oke, 1987; Oke et al., 2017). The term 'island' in UHI stems from its conceptual representation, illustrating several urban-centred isotherms depicting nocturnal positive air temperature (Oke, 1988; Oke et al., 2017). However, actual urban areas often showcase UHI patterns with diverse configurations, like

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clusters of hotspots or sprawling formations (Oke et al., 2017), as observed, for instance, in Lisbon (Alcoforado et al., 2009; Alcoforado and Andrade, 2006).

In the last decades, a third UHI level has gained increasing attention – the Surface Urban Heat Island (SUHI, Oke et al., 2017). At the surface level, the SUHI is the land surface temperature difference between urban and rural surfaces, usually calculated based on satellite remote sensing thermal imagery. Advancements in satellite remote sensing have granted researchers access to ample thermal imagery datasets, ensuring spatial consistency, frequent observations, and global coverage. Despite its abundance, satellite thermal data faces challenges such as cloud cover interference, the need for appropriate methodologies for atmospheric correction, limited availability of direct LST validation observations, constraints posed by sensor spatial resolution and field of view, as well as the satellite's orbit, which dictates revisit intervals and overpass periods (Anderson et al., 2021).

Such constraints have led to many UHI studies specifically devoted to the surface's thermal response, i.e., SUHI, often using scenes acquired during the day (Liu and Zhang, 2011; Rosenzweig et al., 2006). To a broader audience, conclusions from such data are likely to be misleading, since:

- during the day, all but tree covered canopy surfaces tend to show a 'warming' signal in the LST, and the urban 'outline' is not distinguishable from other warm surfaces, such as scattered vegetation, grasslands, rock or bare soil that warm up at a similar rate as urban surfaces as soon as they dry up – this is especially problematic during the dry summer season, in mid latitude regions, as in the Mediterranean;
- at the canopy layer level, the UHI is a nocturnal effect, while an Urban Cooling Island (UCI) prevails during the day – hence, the daily cycle of the urban-rural air temperature differences does not agree with the diurnal SUHI pattern (Chrysoulakis et al., 2018); and

- the Urban Energy Balance (UEB) components are not usually addressed in remote sensing studies – in fact, identifying the evapotranspiration reduction due to low vegetation cover, together with the enhanced diurnal surface heat storage, is the most meaningful diurnal satellite-based information for a local UHI analysis, as both are responsible for the greater nocturnal urban air temperature (Oke et al., 2017).

While urban climate literature typically aims to describe atmospheric UHI processes, spatial patterns, and magnitudes, access to intra-urban air temperature measurements is often limited in terms of spatial coverage, temporal continuity, and data quality (Chapman et al., 2017; Napoly et al., 2018). Indeed, most cities do not have in-situ networks dense enough to provide air temperature datasets with adequate spatial resolution. In contrast, remote sensing thermal imagery from missions like Landsat, MODIS, or Sentinel-3 offers readily available data at higher spatial resolutions (ranging from 100m to 1km), ensuring global coverage and continuity for various case studies (Bechtel et al., 2012; Cai et al., 2018). However, it should be noticed that a third UHI type, the SUHI, has quite specific spatio-temporal patterns and magnitudes, which should not be considered representative of the atmospheric ones (Oke et al., 2017). As the SUHI magnitude depicts the urban-rural differences of LST, a SUHI effect may also be present during the day, as satellite imagery provides a bird's eye view, and corresponding thermal imagery is greatly influenced by the roof surface materials.

As a result, the main issue with SUHI measurement is related to the 'Granularity versus Spatial Resolution dilemma' (Anderson et al., 2021), and how it restricts the LST usage as an UHI proxy. Urban studies require sub-kilometre spatial resolutions to comprehensively assess different thermal performances within urban fabrics. Currently, this resolution is typically provided by Low Earth Orbit (LEO) satellites like Landsat (e.g., Landsat 8/9) but comes with drawbacks such as large revisit times (less than 2 images per month per satellite; (USGS, 2019) and limited availability of scenes acquired during mid-morning hours, which are unsuitable for UHI assessment due to the absence of atmospheric UHI effects.

In addition, only the scenes acquired during the diurnal descending orbit of the Landsat satellites, are usually made publicly available. This corresponds to the mid-morning hours of the day, in mid-latitude regions, which is not suitable for UHI assessment – at this time of the day, the atmospheric UHI effect is typically absent, as the urban surfaces already emitted the previous day's stored heat during the night, and have not yet received enough additional solar radiation to provide a clear 'urban signal' (Oliveira et al., 2020).

Alternatively, nocturnal thermal imagery is available from other missions, such as those acquired by the Terra and Aqua Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (Terra/Aqua MODIS) or the Sentinel-3 Sea LST Radiometer (Sentinel 3 SLSTR) – all are LEO satellites, providing two images per day, but with a 1km-pixel spatial resolution. Nonetheless, their nocturnal LST products have been shown to provide good insights into the UHI effect in larger cities, even with a lower level of detail (Shumilo et al., 2019; Ünal et al., 2020). On the other hand, satellites in geostationary orbit, like those from the GOES or Meteosat missions, offer temporal granularity up to sub-hourly intervals. However, their spatial resolution is limited to kilometre scale, making them less suitable for detailed intra-urban analysis. Considering Lowry's components contributing to a given local weather element, to properly address climate change adaptation strategies, in the Oceanic (Copenhagen) cities, one must consider the regional scale of heat and coldwave (HW and CW) events. These extreme temperature events often span hundreds of kilometres, impacting both rural and urban areas. Despite this regional scale, the UEB and its influence on various layers of the UHI can shed light on potential interactions between regional and local factors. While some studies (Founda and Santamouris, 2017) suggest a correlation between HW and UHI intensification, others (Oliveira et al., 2021) present contrasting findings, particularly for the Lisbon region.

Despite the diurnal acquisition-related constraints, Landsat-based diurnal surface heat fluxes have been shown to provide greater insights on the culprit of the atmospheric UHI signal – particularly, the diurnal storage heat flux has been noted for being much greater in

impervious/artificial urban surfaces during the mid-morning overpass, which partially contributes to the greater availability of nocturnal sensible heat in the atmosphere (see Oliveira et al., 2022, for a comprehensive discussion). The diurnal latent heat flux is also affected by the absence of extensive green coverage and is reduced in urban areas, which negatively affects natural cooling processes. Hence, the spatial patterns of the diurnal heat flux components are known to explain the corresponding nocturnal atmospheric temperature anomaly (Oke, 1988; Oke et al., 2017; Parlow, 2021).

To address these challenges, open data science methodologies can integrate diverse datasets, including discrete point observations and remote sensing products, to develop and validate empirical models for data fusion, useful for assessing urban thermal performance. These approaches offer cost-effective solutions for understanding heat exposure and informing urban planning strategies.

1.1.2 Gap Analysis

While the complexity of studying urban climate requires a broad understanding, it is essential to translate these large-scale patterns into localised insights, especially for effective policy-making and urban planning. Downscaling plays a crucial role in urban climate research, converting broad-scale data into detailed, city-specific information. For instance, while UHI intensification trends during HW are noticeable across Europe, downscaling can refine these trends to offer nuanced insights for cities, as demonstrated in Lisbon pilot studies and planned for Copenhagen, Aarhus, Odense, and Aalborg. Such models can achieve higher spatial resolutions, enabling the identification of spatial patterns through the integration of local in-situ data with Earth Observation (EO), reducing the underestimation errors which is a typical feature of modelled data, such as numerical weather predictions (NWP) or earth systems climate models (ESM).

Fine-scale climate information assumes that local conditions result from the interplay of large-scale atmospheric elements like circulation patterns, temperature, and moisture, in combination with geographic features like water bodies, mountains, and land

characteristics. While physical models capture these interactions to reveal relationships between current local climate and broader atmospheric conditions, a process known as model downscaling (Hernanz et al., 2022), the integration between scales and boundary conditions is very complex, and entails long iterations and runs to reach mature results. On the other hand, while data-driven models are more closely fed with observational data, their non-deterministic nature means that their performance is dependent on good quality inputs and sensible hyper parameterisation choices. In some cases, these ML models tend to become very good at predicting situations similar to those they were trained for, but fail to generalise well when confronted with prediction setups outside of the training data scope. Hence, both of these techniques have inherent limitations and uncertainties. The analysis identified the following main gaps:

1. Limitations in Downscaling

Statistical downscaling establishes empirical relationships between large-scale atmospheric variables (predictors) and localised climate conditions (predictands), while dynamical downscaling simulates local climates using regional climate models (RCMs) or high-resolution global models. However, statistical downscaling relies heavily on historical data, which might not remain valid in future climate scenarios (Hernanz et al., 2022), and dynamical downscaling requires significant computational resources and detailed input data (USAID, 2014). Each method has unique limitations:

- i) Statistical methods can oversimplify the complex relationships between large-scale and local climate conditions, often overlooking the energy balance components critical for accurate assessments of UHI intensity.
- ii) Dynamical models are constrained by their assumptions, high computational demands, and the need for comprehensive input data, which are often limited due to the lack of high-density mesoscale weather networks and intra-urban air temperature measurements.

Both approaches can struggle with predictive accuracy in regions where broad-to-local climate correlations are weak. Additionally, there is a decoupling between surface temperature anomaly and canopy layer temperature anomaly, complicating the assessments of daily cycle differences. A hybrid method combining statistical and dynamical approaches can mitigate these issues by blending empirical data relationships with the detailed physics of regional climate processes (USAID, 2014).

2. Challenges of Computational and Data Constraints

Dynamical downscaling demands significant computational resources and requires comprehensive input data, particularly for regions with complex terrain or scarce localised data (USAID, 2014). The detailed input data required includes high-resolution topographical, land use, and soil information. In many cases, data availability is limited or outdated, which significantly affects the model's accuracy. This challenge is exacerbated by the scarcity of high-density mesoscale weather networks and the decoupling between surface and canopy layer UHI measurements. The computational requirements of these models also pose challenges, often necessitating powerful computing clusters for timely simulations. Efficient processing methods, such as cloud computing or distributed systems, can alleviate computational constraints. Enhanced data-sharing frameworks would provide regions with access to high-quality input data like topographical and land use information. Furthermore, predictive models should be developed with flexibility in mind, accommodating varying data availability and computational capacities.

3. Machine Learning (ML) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) Overfitting

ML and AI models offer significant potential for modelling complex climate patterns due to their ability to identify nonlinear relationships within vast datasets. However, these models are not without challenges. They are prone to overfitting when data is sparse, particularly in regions with limited historical climate observations. Additionally, the decoupling of surface and canopy layer temperatures can lead to misguided conclusions if not properly

addressed. Furthermore, interpretability is a major concern because ML/AI models often function as "black boxes," making it challenging to understand the underlying processes that lead to their predictions (Meier et al., 2017). This lack of transparency is problematic in climate science, where understanding the reasoning behind predictions is crucial for decision-makers. To leverage the potential of ML and AI while minimising their limitations, these models should be rigorously compared with statistical and dynamical downscaling approaches to identify their strengths and weaknesses in various contexts. Uncertainties from using ML/AI modelling approaches will be systematically tackled through WP2000 ML Architectures Benchmark and WP4000 MLOps Description and Validation, especially during the ML Architectures Benchmark stage (WP2000). This will involve an iterative process of data acquisition, handling, model training, and testing. This approach aims to explore numerous alternatives to identify the best combinations of inputs and model parameters.

By leveraging the consortium's robust big data processing infrastructure, our focus will be on preventing overfitting and improving model generalisation capabilities. This will be achieved through the adoption of rigorous and well-established ML protocols. Additionally, we will address potential signals arising from autocorrelation within the data structure, whether spatial, temporal, or individual. A key strategy will be diversifying spatial and temporal coverage to mitigate these challenges, ultimately enhancing the ML/AI models' ability to detect complex patterns that lead to HW/CW events.

4. Quality Assurance Challenges for Crowdsourced Observations

Crowdsourced weather data offers unprecedented granularity and high-resolution insights, but the reliability of this data can be compromised due to poor sensor placement, calibration issues, and varying data quality. For instance, systematic errors in citizen observations often stem from inadequate station placement, leading to diurnally varying biases (Nipen et al., 2020; Chapman et al., 2017). Moreover, sensors lack regular

maintenance or calibration, and the lack of metadata makes identifying problematic stations challenging. Additionally, integrating citizen-sourced weather data into modelling frameworks is difficult due to potential unreliability, leading to subpar predictions. Despite the identified constraints, the density and volume of citizen-contributed data provide unique opportunities to capture localised weather patterns if quality control protocols can be standardised. Quality control (QC) methods, such as those proposed by Napoly et al. (2018), should be standardised to ensure reliable crowdsourced data. These protocols can include statistical identification of suspect observations and elevation corrections. Establishing calibration guidelines and incentivising best practices for sensor placement will help maintain data integrity. Furthermore, advanced statistical methods can help correct biases, identify errors, and ensure that crowdsourced data is integrated effectively into modelling frameworks. A collaborative approach involving citizen scientists, weather agencies, and research institutions is crucial for improving data quality while encouraging continued participation.

5. Lack of Comprehensive Integrated Urban Environment and Climate Services

Cities, especially coastal areas, have unique vulnerabilities. However, adopting high-resolution numerical weather prediction (NWP) models tailored to these city-specific processes poses significant challenges due to their computational demands, the need for comprehensive data inputs, and difficulties in accurately modelling the boundary conditions (Baklano et al., 2018; Grimmond and WMO, 2014). Without accurate, localised data acquisition networks that account for geographic characteristics and phenomena, many cities are unable to capture relevant information at the required spatial and temporal resolutions. The lack of high-density mesoscale weather networks, intra-urban air temperature measurements, and the challenge of integrating citizen-sourced data into modelling frameworks further complicate this issue. Localised observational networks should be prioritised to capture urban climate phenomena with adequate spatial and temporal detail. Building robust collaborative frameworks between municipalities, research

institutions, and private data providers is critical to standardise data-sharing protocols and improve data acquisition methods. Feedback loops between city-level administrations, data providers, and model developers are essential to ensure that integrated urban climate services are effective. Continued research into simplifying high-resolution NWP models can make them more accessible for city planners, while emerging technologies like thermal sensors could help bridge data gaps in urban regions (Leroux et al., 2023).

1.1.3 Earth Observation for Urban Climate Services

Urban settlements are growing worldwide. A larger fraction of people are living in urban environments, and at the same time the larger, more dense urban areas are impacted by climate change (Kumar et al., 2024). The challenges urban areas are facing are many, and EO plays a vital role in monitoring many of them (Upreti et al., 2024).

An area where EO is already an integral part of global urban climate services is in the temporal development of the urban areas. Whether it is measuring densification of built-up areas (Chauhan et al., 2024; Kaspersen et al., 2015) or development of green spaces (Dosiadis et al., 2024; Shahtahmassebi et al., 2021), EO plays a central role in mapping year-to-year development in these key descriptors for understanding urban development (Kumar et al., 2024).

For urban application, the challenge lies with effects that are present in high spatio-temporal resolution. Most EO products are not directly available at temporal scales, therefore they are not able to track diurnal variations, and at the same time, the spatial resolution is not resolving urban features (Guha et al., 2024; Singh et al., 2024). For that reason, a lot of effort is put into downscaling and utilising the EO products at scales relevant in the urban context (Chauhan et al., 2024); here ML approaches are at the forefront of development (Kumar and Bassill, 2024; Perikamana et al., 2024).

Several examples of EO driven urban climate services exist, a market segment increasingly run on commercial terms where private parties deliver services where EO is an integral and, sometimes, hidden underlying part (Ravichandran, 2023). The GEOSS Portal (www.geoportal.org) is an example of a tool that seeks to provide a one-stop entrance to services built on EO. It links to ~12 million studies, services and tools whereof ~17 thousand have an “urban” angle to them. Most of these services are not climate services per se, but map single variables that are relevant in climate services (e.g. vegetation cover, or urban density). As such, they appear more as intermediate products that process EO data to a format where users can feed them into climate services, that in the end can help end users. The Copernicus Urban Atlas (Dijkstra and Poelman, 2012; European Commission, 2022) is one public and open example of an urban climate service where cross continental EO data is used to map relevant urban variables and their development in time. The focus of this is on land use/land cover and buildings and trees. Currently, there exists three time slices covering 2006, 2012 and 2018 with further updates planned to include more time slices. The results are presented as vector data and the minimum resolution of features are 0.25 ha.

There is also the meteorological and climate predictions angle to consider. In response to the already documented health impacts of HWs and the projected intensification of these extreme events in the future, the development of heat-health Early Warning Systems (EWS) has been put forth as one of the main priorities of the World Meteorological Organization (WMO) and the World Health Organization (WHO), in terms of the global climate change agenda. While the definition and requirements for EWS is still an ongoing exercise by the community, it can broadly be defined as a system that combines meteorological forecasts to trigger public health actions, in order to reduce heat-related impacts such as excess mortality, hospital admissions and morbidity. EWS should be built upon the establishment of reliable thresholds for determining the human tolerance to extreme heat, but those are still unstandardised, with ongoing debates regarding which

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algorithm formulation and reference values should be used. Many studies describe case-specific relationships but there are very few and limited examples of consolidated systems (Casanueva et al., 2019). For example, in Europe, many EWS are based upon empirical knowledge on total all-cause mortality data, using it as the response variable from which to derive the temperature threshold that triggers nation-wide warnings, whereas EWS in Germany and Austria are based on heat-budget models evaluating thermal discomfort and stress levels based on the expected response from a 'typical human'. Furthermore, in many cases, EWS are defined at the country level (i.e., same reference value for the whole country), with few examples of local-specific algorithms (including England, France, Germany, Greece, Italy and Spain). But as heat exposure is aggravated by the UHI effect, there is enough urban specificity to support the need for local-adjusted predictions and applications, improving the weather and climate data spatial level of detail, and supporting the evaluation of amelioration actions, such as the implementation of nature-based solutions (NBS).

A noteworthy initiative focused on such EO-based climate services is the Group on Earth Observation (GEO) and World Meteorological Organization (WMO) Global Heat Resilience Service: The Global Heat Resilience Service will provide essential, city-specific information to help improve public health, the economy, and urban development in response to extreme heat, now and into the future. Using a mix of data sources, including satellites, field measurements, local surveys, and geospatial data, the service will help cities to better understand and prepare for heat-related risks. The service will be a key input for the delivery of a [Global Early Warning System for All](#) which will be developed by 2027 as part of a commitment by the UN Secretary General.

1.2 Scientific, Technical and User Requirements [WP1200]

1.2.1 User Requirements

CLIM4cities takes advantage of the proximity between DMI and local stakeholders, as the entity responsible for national weather and climate services. In this regard, preliminary discussions held during the Danish Climate Atlas development (Climate Change Adaptation, 2022), allow to emphasise the main benefits that the users pursue:

- support for early warning-based decision-making and response; and
- support for strategic preparedness and long-term adaptation decisions.

Accordingly, the above-listed entities and sectors represent well-known impacts of air temperature extremes that may be modulated locally by the UHI:

- **Health:** historical data in Europe (Masselot et al., 2023) has proved that there is a significant and strong relationship between air temperature heat extremes and excess mortality; morbidity studies are scarcer and mostly national or region-specific, due to difficulties in accessing such data, but existing literature indicates excess emergency calls; nonetheless, in Denmark, there are contradictory findings depending on the whether the authors use absolute air temperature or percentile-based approaches to identify the extremes (Masselot et al., 2023; Wichmann et al., 2011). Still, the summer of 2018 proved to be unusually warmer (and drier) which led the Danish Emergency Management Agency (DEMA) to add a new chapter to their National Risk Profile (Danish Emergency Management Agency, 2022) highlighting potential stress on the healthcare sector, as per that year's example when «There were a record number of dehydration- and heat stroke-related hospital admissions. The heat was estimated to have caused an excess mortality of 250, primarily among elderly individuals»;

- **Energy:** the same report also states that the «Danish population is not used to – and buildings are not well equipped for – extremely high temperatures» which may lead to pressure over on the electricity sector (e.g., overwhelmed systems and power outages, affecting areas of society highly dependent on electricity and critical installations that have a special need for cooling). The same report also provides a recent example from 2018, «in the energy sector, the heat triggered an unanticipated energy need for cooling. Danish wind turbines could not keep up and solar panels could not compensate for the missing wind. The energy demand was therefore met by imported energy, causing energy prices to rise by 66 per cent in July as compared to the previous year»;
- **Spatial and Land-use Planning:** while Denmark has a limited time series of historical HW events, the potential aggravation of air temperatures within urban areas is also referred to as potentially problematic. Spatial planning and urban climate are deeply interconnected, but the anomaly introduced by urbanisation is smaller (i.e., usually on the order of 2–5°C) when compared to the natural variability of the weather (average monthly air temperature in Copenhagen between 1981–2010 was 1.4°C in January and 18.1°C in July, according to observational data from DMI (Cappelen, 2021)). Hence, this sector is mostly concerned with using higher resolution models for scenario making, to plan ahead for the future climate and to optimise the definition of land use plans towards more resilient and healthy living, for instance, by testing the models' sensitivity to the introduction of more green or blue infrastructure. Although such experiences may not provide as detailed results as if it were by conducting controlled experiments through physics-based models, they can serve as a first approach for a qualitative first assessment at the broader metropolitan and municipal scales.

In the **CLIM4cities** project we have conducted user needs workshops and bilateral discussions with relevant stakeholders, in order to update and sharpen the user needs in relation to an UHI data product. Within the project the following events have taken place:

- April 9th, 2024: Workshop in Copenhagen with participation of the Municipalities of Copenhagen, Frederiksberg and Lyngby-Taarbæk, the Capital Region and Region Zealand, The Danish Environmental Protection Agency, University of Copenhagen and the green think tank, Concito.
- April 15th, 2024: Workshop in Aarhus with participation of the Municipalities of Aalborg and Odense, the Regions of Southern and Central Denmark and Aalborg University.
- May 8th, 2024: Bilateral discussion with Local Government Denmark (the Danish association for Danish municipalities).
- May 15th and 17th, 2024: Further bilateral discussions with the University of Copenhagen, Department of Public Health and Department of Geoscience and Natural Resource Management.
- May 17th, 2024: Bilateral discussions with the Municipality of Aarhus.
- May 27th, 2024: Further bilateral discussion with the Municipality of Copenhagen.

Table 1 Outcome of the user need workshops conducted in Copenhagen and Aarhus, April 2024.

Role	Expressed needs	Possible implications for CLIM4cities
Municipal planner	There is a strong wish to have UHI data for present and future conditions available for planning in as high a spatial resolution as is technically possible. Planning data is generally available at cadastre level resolution in Denmark, and the municipalities therefore have skills and procedures in place to be able to work with information at that level of detail.	UHI output maps have to be produced in as high spatial resolution as possible. Focus on maximum expected temperature as well as maximum UHI effect
Municipal planner	As other information is available at very high spatial resolution, there is a strong need for a breakdown of the model results, in order for the end-users to be able to understand which parts of the underlying city morphology that causes pixel-to-pixel differences. This will be a strong tool for practitioners when differences between apparently similar areas are detected, and mitigation efforts are to be designed.	The level of detail of the documentation of the ML model used for the UHI downscaling has to be high. Further, distinctions between input variables have to be explicit and well described.
Municipal planner, regional planner	Focus at the municipal level is very much on mitigation, and for that purpose, there is a strong wish to have access to the ML model, and use it for running scenarios with potential land use changes reflecting possible mitigation efforts through e.g. Nature-Based Solutions, as well as the expected effects of urban development, densification and sprawl.	A version of the ML model that can easily be rerun with altered input data in the form of GIS layers representing the urban morphology.
Municipal planner, regional planner	In line with the above need, a catalogue of the expected effects on UHI of possible mitigation efforts is sought after as a planning tool.	Is beyond CLIM4cities and the purpose of DMI, but could potentially be built using the ML model by others.
Emergency management at all levels	An operational UHI warning system where authorities with a few days lead-time can react to the extra effect of UHI in HW situations. Here, the wish is to be able to map out better which areas people should avoid due to extreme heat, and where in the cities people can go to experience the coolest conditions.	Is potentially beyond CLIM4cities , but could be forwarded to the relevant part of DMI for further development as soon as we have a good idea about the UHI effects in Denmark. Could build on the ML models from CLIM4cities .
Regional climate adaptation coordinator	Perspectives beyond the pure urban municipalities. Especially the question of how small cities can expect to have an UHI effect.	Is beyond CLIM4cities , but the developed ML model can be used by DMI afterwards on more, smaller, Danish cities in order to be able to map out which size cities should have in order to have a distinct UHI effect that should be dealt with in planning situations.
Regional health authorities, health impact research	During HWs, excess deaths are reported, and the causes of those are a mixture of personal vulnerability and heat related effects. The personal vulnerability is quite well understood and described in the Danish context, but the heat exposure related risk would benefit from high resolution spatial data on UHI.	UHI output maps have to be produced in as high spatial resolution as possible, and actually the need is for even higher resolution than what is expected to be possible within CLIM4cities .

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1.2.2 Technical & Scientific Requirements

In alignment with the established requirements and the goal of this deliverable, the work in this section encompassed a more adjusted description of the target downscaling models and datasets for geospatial, citizen-owned weather station data quality control and computational capacity requirements.

1.2.2.1 Data Gathering and Pre-processing

Geospatial Data

To ensure the accuracy and robustness of the ML models, a comprehensive understanding and utilisation of diverse input datasets is essential. These datasets (Table 2 to Table 5) encompass a wide range of sources, including in-situ observations, EO data, geospatial products, and outputs from numerical weather predictions (NWP).

A comprehensive analysis of the initially proposed datasets was conducted to ensure their suitability for the ML models. The tables in this section list the selected datasets for the T2m and LST downscaling. Table 2 describes the datasets that will be considered for the LST downscaling model, more specifically, the datasets that will be used for down sampling (Sentinel-3) and validation (Landsat 8/9). After sampling existing LST data sources and having in consideration the operational status of these missions, as well as the users' requirements of regular updates, **CLIM4cities** is opting to discard other data sources that have no temporal continuity to the present and in the near future – this is the case of ESA-CCI LST products, which are supplied as historical time series only, or MODIS data, which is in decommissioning phase. Opting for Sentinel-3 thus allows co-registration of required optical and thermal bands inputs, as well as expected short latency updates and future data continuity. Even though not explicitly mentioned in table 2, geostationary data might be also considered as ancillary inputs for LST downscaling, if needed (e.g., from Meteosat/SEVIRI), particularly level 4 products such as LS, evapotranspiration or turbulent heat fluxes.

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Table 2 Satellite data and products (optical and thermal imagery)

Satellite	Sensor	Spatial coverage	Spatial resolution	Temporal resolution	Time span	Source
Landsat 8	TIRS	Global	100 m	16 days	2013–present	https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov
	OLI	Global	30m (VIS, NIR, SWIR)	16 days	2013–present	
Landsat 9	TIRS-2	Global	100m	16 days	2021 – present	
	OLI-2		30m			
Sentinel-3	SLSTR	Global	1 km	Twice daily	2016–present	https://scihub.copernicus.eu/
	OLCI	Global	300 m			

Regarding the LST downscaling model, the instruments chosen for daily sub-kilometric LST production were the Sea and LST Radiometer (SLSTR) and the Ocean and Land Colour Imager (OLCI). SLSTR data products are processed at three levels (Level-0, Level-1, and Level-2), with Levels 1 and 2 being publicly accessible. Level-1 products provide calibrated radiances and brightness temperatures (RBT) for each channel on the instrument grid for both nadir and oblique views, along with some ancillary data. Level-2 products include, among other things, sea surface temperature (SST), LST, and fire radiative power (Philippe Goryl et al. 2012). The official SLSTR LST product algorithm is a split-window algorithm (SWA) that implicitly assumes and uses knowledge of land surface emissivity (LSE):

Equation 1

$$LST = a_0 + b_0 T_{11} + c_0 T_{12}$$

where a_0 , b_0 and c_0 are classes of coefficients that depend on atmospheric water vapour, satellite viewing angle and land surface emissivity. T_{11} and T_{12} represent the brightness

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temperatures measured at 11 μm and 12 μm respectively (Philippe Goryl et al. 2012). The images produced by OLCI are provided on-board for maritime, land, atmospheric and climate change monitoring. The OLCI sensor consists of 21 spectral channels ranging from about 400 nm to 1020 nm (i.e., from the visible to near-infrared wavelengths) with a fine spectral resolution. Owing to the global spatial coverage and fine spectral and temporal resolutions, the Sentinel-3 OLCI images are suitable to produce spectral indices such as NDVI, NDWI, and BI2 (Z. Wang, Sui, and Zhang 2022).

The synergistic operation of Sentinel-3A and Sentinel-3B satellites provides a temporal resolution of about 0.5 days for SLSTR and OLCI data, beneficial for frequent monitoring. The spatial resolution of 1 km for SLSTR and 300 m for OLI products ensures the synchronous availability of spectral indices per LST scene, necessary for effective down sampling. Moreover, as Sentinel 3 is part of a fairly new mission expected to update its constellation and continue operations into the next decades, it guarantees long-term data continuity and reliability. In the case of the LST model, as previously mentioned, the consortium shall evaluate the downscaling accuracy of the LST model based on high resolution Landsat 8/9 LST products.

Table 3 presents a variety of Earth Observation (EO) products. These will be used as fixed inputs for both models. Many of these products portray stable or gradually changing geographical features of the Area of Interest (AoI), such as terrain and land cover attributes.

To construct the LST model, the fixed input variables to be considered include Digital Elevation Model (DEM) data to understand and adjust for the influences of topography on temperature readings. The classification of local climate zones (LCZ), known as LCZ-based Bowen Ratio (LCZBR), will also be considered as it impacts the distribution and behaviour of heat fluxes, thus influencing the predicted LST. Additional geographic features and land cover information will be tested to refine the prediction model based on regional specifics affecting temperature distributions. The LST is a function of the energy balance at the surface, which includes incoming and outgoing radiation as well as sensible and latent heat

fluxes. To improve the accuracy of the LST downscaling model, heat fluxes will be calculated and applied. Sensible heat flux (H) and latent heat flux (LE) are key components of the surface energy balance that influence the temperature of the land surface. By incorporating these fluxes, we can better capture the variations in LST due to the dynamic interactions between the surface and the atmosphere. At the UCL level, the UEB can be calculated as follows:

Equation 2

$$Q_{net} (+ QF) = QE + QH + \delta QG (+ \delta QA)$$

Where Q_{net} is the net radiation, QF is the anthropogenic heat (released from human activities, such as from vehicles exhaust or air condition systems), QH the turbulent sensible heat flux density, QE is the turbulent latent heat flux density, δQG is the net storage heat flux, and δQA is the net heat advection. Both QF and δQA terms are neglected in this study as (i) the former's remote sensing based calculation is still under study and its weight in the energy balance is considered small (Wicki et al., 2018), and (ii) the latter's effect during synoptically stable HW events can be neglected (Wicki et al., 2018). The Q_{net} term can be obtained from:

Equation 3

$$Q_{net} = SW\downarrow + SW\uparrow + LW\downarrow + LW\uparrow$$

Where $SW\downarrow$ and $SW\uparrow$ are the upwelling and downwelling shortwave radiances, and $LW\downarrow$ and $LW\uparrow$ are the longwave atmospheric counter radiation and terrestrial emission, respectively. Sentinel-3 does not directly provide downwelling shortwave radiation, but it can be estimated using models and atmospheric correction algorithms applied to the Sentinel-3 OLCI data, which provides top-of-atmosphere (TOA) reflectance. The upwelling can be calculated using the surface albedo (α) derived from Sentinel-3 OLCI surface reflectance products and the downwelling shortwave radiation:

Equation 4

$$SW\uparrow = \alpha \cdot SW\downarrow$$

Similar to the shortwave radiation, the downwelling longwave radiation can be estimated using atmospheric models in combination with Sentinel-3 SLSTR data, which provides surface temperature and emissivity data. The upwelling longwave radiation can be calculated using LST from Sentinel-3 SLSTR and the surface emissivity:

Equation 5

$$LW\uparrow = \epsilon \cdot \sigma \cdot LST^4 + (1 - \epsilon) \cdot LW\downarrow$$

Where σ is the Stefan-Boltzmann constant ($5.67 \times 10^{-8} \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-4}$).

Table 3 Satellite-based data products

Variable name	Dataset	Spatial Resolution	Temporal Resolution	Source
Urban Atlas LCLU 2018	Urban Atlas(UA) 2018	10m (MMU)	Updated every 6 years	https://land.copernicus.eu/local/urban-atlas/urban-atlas-2018
Land Use Land Cover	Corine Land Cover (CLC)	25 ha (MMU)	6 years	https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/corine-land-cover
Imperviousness Density	IMD	10 m	3 years	https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/high-resolution-layers/imperviousness/status-maps
Tree Cover Density	TCD	10 m	3 years	https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/high-resolution-layers/forests/tree-cover-density/status-maps
Dominant Leaf Type	DLT	10 m	3 years	https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/high-resolution-layers/forests/dominant-leaf-type
Grasslands	GRA	20 m	3 years	https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/high-resolution-layers/grassland/status-maps/grassland-2018
Cropland	OpenStreet Map	n/a	n/a	https://www.openstreetmap.org/#map=7/39.602/-7.839
High Resolution Vegetation Phenology and Productivity	Vegetation Indices	10 m	daily	https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/biophysical-parameters/high-resolution-vegetation-phenology-and-productivity
Digital Elevation Model	European Digital Elevation Model (EU-DEM)	25 m	Updated Every 11 years	http://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/satellite-derived-products/eu-dem/eu-dem-v1.1/view

The usage of NWP data (see Table 4) is primarily focused on the development of the near surface air temperature ML model, as the source for the synoptic scale background weather conditions. As previously mentioned, for the study in the Lisbon pilot, the approach yielded good results, therefore preference was given to the HARMONIE-AROME

2.5km model. To construct the T2m model, the input variables considered include hourly background meteorological conditions from operational NWP and layers describing the natural landscape and urban climate proxies that are fixed in time. Meteorological inputs will include air temperature at 2m, relative humidity, wind speed and direction, and mean surface level pressure, laid out in a grid with 2.5–5 km spatial resolution. Additionally, two Boolean variables, derived from NWP air temperature data, will indicate the presence of extreme temperature events, such as HW or CW, identified using distinct percentiles. Variables to describe the landscape include altitude, topographic exposure index (per octant, based on the prevailing wind direction at each time step), distance to the estuary/coast, tree coverage density, degree of imperviousness, and the Land Use/Land Cover (LULC)-based Bowen Ratio. These will be integrated into a detailed urban grid to interpolate the upscaled forecasts.

Table 4 NWP models information

Name	Source	Type	Domain	Variables of interest	Grid size	Timesteps	Forecast length	Run times (UTC)	Cost	Access
HARMONIE-AROME	Danish Meteorological Institute - DMI	Deterministic, regional	Greenland (IGB) and Northwestern Europe (NEA)	TMP2m	~2.5 km	hourly	0-18 hours	00, 03, 06, 09, 12, 15, 18, 21	free	HTTP
HIRLAM	FMI	Deterministic, regional	Europe	TMP2m	~5x7 km	hourly	3 days	00, 06, 12	free	HTTP, AWS-S3
ICON-EU	DWD	Deterministic, regional	Europe	TMP2	~5x7 km	hourly	2 days	00, 03, 06, 09, 12, 15, 18, 21	free	HTTP

Lastly, the validation of the effectiveness of additional spectral indices, land cover and land use (LCLU), urban morphological characteristics, and other pertinent geographic data

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layers for targeted surface-specific downscaling results will be conducted. Through these measures, we aim to enhance the precision and applicability of the products across various domains.

Citizen Owned Weather Station Data

In the case of the T2m model, after computing the input variables for each station for the period of interest, temperature measurements from the stations that are extracted, undergo a series of Quality Control steps, and the approved temperature values then serve as target variables for model training and validation. Dealing with crowdsourced meteorological data, like that from Citizen Weather Stations (CWS), presents several challenges. These include incorrect station placement due to unfamiliarity with World Meteorological Organization standards, inadequate station maintenance, and inconsistencies in time series data. Such issues can lead to contamination of the target variable with inaccurate or outlier data. Given these challenges, rigorous quality control is essential for accurate and reliable modelling. In Denmark, Netatmo is the leading Internet of Things (IoT) solution due to its widespread deployment, provider-claimed high accuracy, API data accessibility, and numerous quality control studies validating its utility. In contrast, alternatives like FieldSense and Lonobox lack comprehensive QC studies and have limited data access, making them less appealing and therefore excluded from the project.

Figure 3 shows the stations that were accepted after the application of the developed quality control routine. Currently, the routine consist in:

- Identifying Suspect Location Entries

Data from stations with identical longitude and latitude are marked as NaN because they are likely to have automatically assigned locations based on the IP address. This indicates a probable setup error by the station owner.

- Elevation Correction

The corrected temperature readings are calculated by incorporating altitude information obtained from high-resolution digital elevation models. A standard atmospheric lapse rate of $0.0065^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{m}$ is utilised to correct temperatures according to elevation disparities from a reference altitude. An adaptive correction is employed in certain atmospheric conditions that might disrupt the standard lapse rate assumptions. Anomaly detection leveraging robust statistical methods identifies and marks outlier readings, categorising them as NaN when they deviate beyond established thresholds.

- Outliers Removal

After applying the altitude-based temperature corrections, each temperature reading is standardised by computing its z-score. Usually, this score is calculated by subtracting the mean temperature of the dataset and dividing by the standard deviation. We use a modified z-score method that is more robust against extreme values, utilising the median absolute deviation instead of the standard deviation to better handle skewed distributions. Data points with z-scores exceeding predefined thresholds (typically set at ± 3 for most climatological datasets) are considered outliers. These outliers are flagged and excluded from the dataset by setting their values to NaN.

Figure 3 Maps with distribution of Netatmo stations with data within the four year period (2020–2023) for each Aol a) Aalborg, with 918 stations, b) Copenhagen, with 2223 stations, c) Aarhus, with 1220 stations and d) Odense, with 673 stations.

Figure 4 shows an example of, for one of the Aols (Aalborg), the Netatmo temperature selected data and outliers over time.

Figure 4 Example of the Netatmo selected temperature data for Aalborg

In addition to citizen-owned data, longer time series shall also be retrieved from WMO's in-situ stations data (i.e., the daily surface observations) as well as from the Copernicus Climate Change Services (e.g., E-OBS gridded observations or ERA5 gridded reanalysis) to calculate the air temperature, heat and cold extremes. A promising methodology that foresees the relative contributions of these both aspects are the so-called Excess Heat Factor (EHF) and its CW counterpart (i.e., the Excess Cold Factor, or ECF). The EHF has gained traction as a well-proven indicator of heat-related human health impacts, across mid-latitude climates, namely human mortality and morbidity (Langlois et al., 2013; Nairn and Fawcett, 2013). The rationale supporting the EHF definition is to identify and quantify extreme temperatures as the three-day mean air temperature deviation from the long-term percentile-based climatology, in a given day of the year (DOY), multiplied by the past month acclimatisation index (if > 1) (Nairn and Fawcett, 2013).

As a result, the EHF is a quadratic function of both the long-term and short-term air temperature anomalies, and its magnitude reflects the human acclimatisation to the local climate. Although the EHF does not include humidity in its calculation, it uses daily mean

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temperature (TM) as the simple average between the daily maximum (TX) and minimum (TN) temperature values, which is implicitly affected by relative humidity changes (in dry or temperate summer climates); hence, according to the authors (Nairn and Fawcett, 2013), the EHF provides local public health stakeholders with a simpler but efficient method to estimate potential human excess heat exposure levels, compared to other bioclimatic indices, such as the Universal Thermal Climate Index (UTCI) (Zare et al., 2018), the Physiological Equivalent Temperature (PET) or Apparent Temperature (AT), which require additional weather variables in their calculations (these are usually used in thermal comfort studies).

In Europe, the EHF has been shown to be increasing in several metropolitan areas (Oliveira et al., 2022) – Denmark, in particular, shows a positive and significant historical trend towards more frequent, longer and more intense HW, based on historical gridded data. The EHF calculation is the product of two excess heat sub-indices: (i) the Excess Heat Index Significance (EHI_{sig}), which measures the 3-day difference to the long-term TM percentile (TM_p) based on a given reference period (here, 1961–1990 shall be used, calculated from observational Copernicus data); and (ii) the Excess Heat Index Acclimatization (EHI_{accl}) measures the 3-day TM difference to the average TM of the preceding 30 days. While the former sub-index represents the excess heat as a long-term (climate-scale) anomaly, the later sub-index is intended to measure heat stress as a short-term anomaly, based on the principle that biological systems are less able to cope with a sudden rise in temperature (J. R. Nairn and Fawcett 2014). The two sub-indices are calculated according to Equation 6 and Equation 7, and the EHF as per Equation 8 as follows (J. R. Nairn and Fawcett 2014; L. Alexander and Herold 2016):

Equation 6

$$EHI_{sig} = TM_{(3\text{-day})} - TM_{(90\text{th percentile})}$$

Equation 7

$$EHI_{accl} = TM_{(3\text{-day})} - TM_{(30\text{-day})}$$

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Equation 8

$$EH = EHI_{sig} \cdot x \cdot \text{MAX}(1, EHI_{accl})$$

where TM3-day/TM30-day is the average TM over 3/30 days, respectively (calculated as the average between TN and TX), and TM90p is the 90th percentile of TM for the corresponding calendar day. In the present study, each grid cell's 90th percentile threshold is calculated based on the 1961–1990 30-year baseline period (WMO, 2017), and the annual DOY curve is smoothed using a 15-day moving average (Alexander and Herold, 2016).

Whenever a positive EHF result is detected, its value is a quadratic measure of HW intensity, responding to both the long-term and short-term anomalies. The measurement unit is °C2L, where the 'L' refers to the local nature of the threshold and EHF results, i.e., results are local-specific, and lower values are expected where the climate temperature range is lower (Nairn et al., 2018). The underlying rationale is the fact that similar quadratic responses to extreme HW have been documented regarding impacts on human health or energy (Hatvani-Kovacs et al. 2016). The ECF formulation is symmetrical to the EHF – so, instead of calculating the positive deviation from the HW percentile, it calculates the negative deviation from the CW percentile. To conduct these calculations, **CLIM4cities** will use alternative percentile thresholds in its formulation (90th, 95th and 99th for the EHF, and 10th, 5th and 1st for the ECF). By adjusting the HW/CW thresholds for classifying extreme events, the ML models can then be analysed in terms of the trade-off between false positives and false negatives extreme values.

To ensure that the models are able to perform well in predicting extreme values, using such indices to identify sets of days when such values are surpassed is a useful strategy. Basically, HW and CW days can be introduced in model training (and testing) as a dummy binary variable to classify days within the time series. It should also be noted that the quadratic nature of these indices is an advantage for training ML models, as the magnitude increases non-linearly for observations at the two tails of the distributions. Hence, such an index can serve as an important predictor for the ML modelling pipeline, both as (i) a

discrete temporal predictor (i.e., a binary classification of extremes) flagging HW/CW, and (ii) as a continuous variable of HW/CW intensity. As a result, **CLIM4cities** shall report the ML models' performance through the comparison between the statistical distribution of the data in the downscaled and observational data, as well as through F1-score and recall (ability of the model in showing extreme values observable during HW/CW).

1.2.2.2 Downscaling Models

The area of interest (AoI) for this task will encompass four Use Case cities: Copenhagen, Aarhus, Odense, and Aalborg, with one city reserved exclusively for unbiased validation. The approach for the T2m downscaling model will be grounded in the framework introduced by Lowry in 1977. This framework highlights the key factors that influence local-specific meteorological measurements, including synoptic weather conditions (background), local-scale natural landscape effects, and the impacts of human-induced alterations of the natural landscape, particularly urban development. The model will utilise input and output variables that are available from at least four years of observational data. The objectives for developing this model include enhancing NWP accuracy, with a target coefficient of determination (R^2) greater than or equal to 0.9 and a mean absolute error (MAE) of 1.5°C, or less – these are the reported benchmark accuracy indicators of existing forecasts (2°C, or more, during heat extremes). Hence, while **CLIM4cities** aims to enhance the spatial resolution by an order of 10, or more, it is also a goal to go beyond the accuracy of the input weather and climate data. The model will also be capable of measuring UHI and SUHI intensities, relative to the background weather/climate, and identify T2m and LST values at a minimum spatial resolution of 250 metres. For this task, three types of algorithms shall be tested and compared: (i) Linear Mixed Models (LMM); (ii) Random Forest Regressions (RF); and (iii) Artificial Neural Networks (ANN). Below, a description of each of these algorithms is provided. Each of them shall be tested during the WP2000 ML Architectures Benchmark development, while LMM will serve as a benchmark regression technique.

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LMM, also referred to as multilevel models, random coefficient models, or hierarchical models, have shown their effectiveness in capturing intricate spatiotemporal relationships among complex climatological variables in urban areas (Oliveira et al, 2021). What distinguishes this model is its ability to accommodate the hierarchical structure of the collected data, for example, for grouping meteorological observations per morphoclimatic class, or to model multi-annual time series according to the seasonal cycle. This hierarchical approach is particularly suitable for handling repeated observations that are unbalanced by sub-groups (e.g., unbalanced spatial distributions, or a significantly spatially clustered structure in the data). When a sufficiently extensive and dense time-series dataset of coarse-resolution LST and high-resolution predictor variables is available, LMM offers the advantage of employing a single model for LST downscaling within a specific area. This contrasts with conventional geospatial downscaling methods, which are effective within a given scene but necessitate model fitting for each new scene encountered. Standardisation of explanatory variables is recommended. LMM model for the ECVs downscaling can be represented as described in Equation 9 (Gelman and Hill, 2006):

Equation 9

$$y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{i1} + (...) + \beta_k x_{ik} + \varepsilon_i \quad , \text{ for observations } i=1, \dots, n$$

where y_i is the response variable, β_0 is the intercept, x_{i1} to x_{ik} are the predictors (or explanatory variables of interest), β_1 to β_k are the effects of each predictor on the response variable, and ε_i is the error term, with normal distribution. By comparison, an LMM can have either different intercepts or different intercepts and slopes, per each of the groups from the nesting structure. As a result, there is an observation-level regression and a group-level regression (here, a regression per scene computed simultaneously). Equation 10 shows an LMM model with random intercept and slope (response variable as y_i), as used in this study, and Equation 11 and Equation 12 show the corresponding equations predicting the intercept (β_{0j}) and slope (β_{1j}):

Equation 10

$$y_i = \beta(O_j[i]) + \beta(1_j[i]) x_{i1} + (\dots) + \beta(k_j[i]) x_{ik} + \epsilon_i, \text{ for observations } i=1, \dots, n$$

Equation 11

$$\beta_{1j} = a_1 + b_{-1} u_j + \eta_{j1}, \text{ for observation groups } j = 1, \dots, k$$

Equation 12

$$\beta_{2j} = a_2 + b_2 u_j + \eta_{j2}, \text{ for observation groups } j = 1, \dots, t$$

where the j subscript corresponds to each different group – here, each time of acquisition. The varying intercept ($\beta(O_j[i])$) and slopes ($\beta(1_j[i])$) to $\beta(k_j[i])$ are modelled at the first and second ‘inner’ levels (Equation 11 and Equation 12), where β_{1j} and β_{2j} depict the group-specific estimated coefficients a_1/a_2 and b_1/b_0 , with corresponding predictor(s) (u_j) and second level errors (η_{j1} and η_{j2}), for group-level observations k and t . Both the a_1/a_2 and b_1/b_2 (per site) parameters are controlled by the hyperparameters of the upper-level fixed structure of the model, characterising each site’s distinct variance, autocorrelation and/or random effect over the predictor (Gelman and Hill, 2006; Zuur et al., 2009). In **CLIM4cities**, we will employ LMM in a similar fashion, to serve as a benchmark regression model for comparison. It should be noted that, while LMM are advantageous because they are less sensitive to outliers, they are, by design, less able to predict true extreme values, but keep the ability of extrapolating whenever relationships are monotonic.

A second architecture to be developed and tested is the RF regression. First introduced by Tin Kam Ho (So T., 1995), it is a supervised learning algorithm built as an ensemble of multiple Decision Tree (DT) models trained independently. It is a very popular model in geospatial ML due its ability to achieve good results without a lot of effort in data wrangling or transformation, since it can learn the underlying complex relationships between variables.

A DT is an intuitive decision-making process that counts with three kinds of elements: nodes, branches and leaves. For making an inference, the process starts at the root node

where the branch to follow is selected based on a given condition. Then the process is repeated in each decision node until we reach a leaf, where we have the output of the model. During the training of the DT model, the conditions to apply in each node are determined so that the leaf nodes match the target variables for each sample of the training dataset. To do so, in each node all the features of the input variables are analysed, and the optimal splitting point (the variable and threshold) is selected based on two quantitative metrics: entropy and information gain. The entropy is a measure of the uncertainty and is used to determine if the current node should split further the dataset or should be a leaf node while the information gain is a measure of how uncertainty in the target variable is reduced and is used to determine the best splitting point to achieve the lower value of entropy after the splitting. However, DT have some drawbacks, one of the main ones being that they usually perform well on the training data but have trouble making predictions on unseen samples, a problem known as over-fitting. Furthermore, they struggle to extrapolate beyond the interval of values used for training. To overcome this constraint, several authors have been pushing for ancillary steps or modified RF versions, for example:

1. Using ensemble or stacked modelling: by merging RF in the scope of several models, including LMM and ANN which are able to extrapolate, RF may be useful because they tend to offer the best performance within typical values. Stacked approaches are usually the closest to best model fit.
2. Employing RF to the residuals: using RF to predict the residuals, instead of the absolute values of T2m and LST (both of which may present underlying trends/covariate shifts), is an alternative, because we transform the time series into a stationary one. Of course, such normalisation procedure can only be used whenever relationships between the predictors and the residuals of the response variables are kept stable throughout their absolute value range.
3. Using Extremal Random Forests: Gneco et al. (2024) propose a method for extreme quantile regression that combines the flexibility of random forests with the theory

of extrapolation, by maximising a local likelihood with weights extracted from a quantile random forest.

4. Using Regression-Enhanced Random Forests: Zhang et al. (2017) also propose an alternative RF method which uses non-parametric penalization and may incorporate known relationships between the response and the predictors, and may give reliable predictions in extrapolation problems where predictions are required at points out of the domain of the training dataset.

In **CLIM4cities**, the RF model shall be one of the ML models trained and fine-tuned, as previous experiences in Lisbon showed that it was able to have the best results during the validation procedures (RF are less computationally "intense" to train), but because of their inherent inability to extrapolate, one or more of the above-mentioned strategies shall be used to overcome this constraint.

Regarding the ANN models, these are vaguely inspired by the way information in our brains is processed. Its structure is set by a stack of layers consisting of an input layer, with all the input variables, a group of hidden layers, where the processing of the input variables occurs, and an output layer, containing the output of the model. The number of hidden layers determines the depth of the ANN and each layer is composed by a group of neurons, which are considered the elementary units of the ANN models. Each neuron of a given layer takes as input all the output values of the previous layer and applies a linear combination to those values. Then, a nonlinear function, known as the activation function, is applied to the output of this linear combination to obtain the output of the neuron.

The weights and biases to use in the linear combination of each neuron of the network are learned during the training process by minimising a loss function, which is a function of the errors in the prediction which is given by comparing the predictions of the model with a target label, previously attributed to each sample of the training data. Having the loss, backpropagation is used to update the weights of the network. This consists in going back through the network, layer by layer, and, for each neuron, using the derivative of the

activation function to update the weights, given the value of the loss function and the chosen optimization algorithm. The training of a Neural Network is an iterative process and given that the adjustments in the weights are very small, it needs several iterations to converge (learn) to a minimum value of the loss function. The number of iterations needed for the optimization is not predictable and it depends on several factors, such as the quality of the training set and the chosen weight update rule. Although the ANN structure allows for large flexibility in terms of the tasks it can tackle, it is also very hard to track the rationale behind each decision of the model. That is why, for many, it is considered a black box model which can be a challenge to deal with when applying the model to real life applications where we need to justify the outputs.

In addition to LMM and RF, the **CLIM4cities** consortium shall also train and fine-tune ANN architectures because they provide more flexibility in the training, for instance, reinforcing certain features during HW/CW to emphasise their role during these extremes, potentially replicating better complex patterns. For instance, ANN can potentially solve very complex problems if a large enough dataset is provided and the NN is large enough, and are better at extrapolating values outside of the training range.

For training these models, two model formulations will be considered. The first consists of predicting the target temperature directly while the second configuration consists of predicting the temperature error, i.e. the difference between the NWP temperature and the Netatmo temperature, and then using this error to correct the NWP value to get the final temperature prediction. Besides these formulations, for the ANN models, besides testing a regression model configuration, which is natural for this model specification, a classification approach will be tested. This involves splitting the output in N bins and using a classification approach to train the model, this way the output can be read as an histogram of the temperature distribution.

During the training phase, various validation techniques, including k-fold cross-validation, will be explored. A crucial consideration is maintaining a balanced representation of HW

and CW events in each dataset split. Given their scarcity within the dataset, HW and CW can be underrepresented, potentially leading the model to neglect learning their specific patterns and focus predominantly on minimising errors in the more frequent standard temperature days. This results in a model that performs well under normal conditions but struggles during HW/CW events. To counteract this, HW and CW data will be augmented in the training set. For each benchmarking step, the Mean Squared Error (MSE) will be assessed on the validation dataset, and the model configuration that achieves the lowest MSE will be chosen as the optimal one. The entire procedure of data pre-processing, model training, and validation is depicted in Figure 5. The proposed approach has been already successfully tested in precursor studies using in-situ, EO and geodata to predict the spatial patterns of the urban energy fluxes, air temperature or the surface and atmospheric UHI intensity (Oliveira, Lopes, et al., 2021; Rigo & Parlow, 2007).

Figure 5 Flowchart of the data pre-processing, model training and validation for the T2m downscaling model

Optimal LST downscaling practices include employing well-established statistical methods like linear regression, which utilises statistical relationships between LST and the selected explanatory variables. The basic idea behind statistical downscaling of LST is the principle of scale invariance, which involves forming a quantitative relation between LST data and influencing factors at varying spatial resolutions. Specifically, a model quantifying the relationship between LST and its influencing factors at coarser spatial resolutions is established. This model is then applied to influencing factors at a higher resolution to create finer-scale LST data. However, differences between the actual and model-predicted

outcomes can occur due to variations in the influencing factors and the diverse nature of land cover. These differences, known as residuals, need to be redistributed throughout the spatial domain and incorporated into the final predicted results. This repetitive adjustment process aims to improve the accuracy of the downscaled LST data at higher spatial resolutions. Our goal here is to minimise error rates and effectively depict extreme events in LST downscaling. The mathematical expression of this simple approach will be as following:

Equation 13

$$LST_{coarse} = f(IF_{coarse})$$

Equation 14

$$LST_{residuals} = LST_{origin} - LST_{coarse}$$

Equation 15

$$LST_{fine} = f(IF_{fine}) + LST_{fine_residuals}$$

Within this context, two of the most well-established and mature algorithms for LST downscaling are DisTrad and TsSHARP. These algorithms employ distinct high spectral resolution indices and employ diverse statistical regression methodologies, both offering precise and consistent results with an error margin of below 2 K RMSE. DisTrad, for instance, leverages the linear relationship between LST and NDVI. The downscaling model's relationship is defined as follows:

Equation 16

$$f_{DisTrad}:LST = a \times NDVI + b$$

where a and b are the constant coefficients obtained by fitting a linear regression to NDVI and LST data. Whereas TsSHARP replaces NDVI with fractional vegetation cover (FVC) that is defined as following:

Equation 17

$$FVC = \frac{1 - NDVI_{min} - NDVI_i}{NDVI_{max} - NDVI_{min}} \times 0.625$$

Over the last ten years, there has been considerable advancement in enhancing the initial downscaling approach through the integration of its fundamental principle into various modelling techniques. These improvements include the adoption of polynomial regression and multiple linear regression (Z. Wang, Sui, and Zhang 2022), along with more complex algorithms designed to understand nonlinear relationships, such as Random Forest (RF) and Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) (Oliveira et al., 2021; Hutengs and Vohland 2016; Njuki, Mannaerts, and Su 2020; Wang, Gao, and Peng 2020). These methods will be evaluated using the same methodological framework as the traditional LST downscaling, which is illustrated in Figure 6.

Figure 6 Flow chart of LST downscaling methodology

1.2.2.3 Evaluation of Model performance

Standard evaluation metrics like MAE, RMSE and R² will be calculated using a final test subset of unbiased observations that were not used in the training of the model. These metrics will help determine the model's accuracy in predicting urban temperature variations seasonally and during specific events such as HW and CW. Additionally, these

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metrics will be reported for different times of the year and for specific event subsets. The performance of our model will also be compared with existing benchmark data, including regional numerical weather prediction forecasts and Copernicus Climate Change products, such as climate variables for European cities from 2008 to 2017, which are derived from the UrbClim model and ERA5 reanalysis inputs.

To ensure effective prediction of extreme values by the models, employing indices to mark days when such extremes occur is a strategic approach. For instance, days characterised by heat and cold extremes (i.e., HW and CW) can be encoded as a binary variable in both model training and testing to classify days within a time series. The quadratic nature of these indices, where the magnitude increases non-linearly at the extremes of the distribution, is beneficial for training ML models. This allows the index to act as a critical predictor in the ML modelling process, serving both as a discrete temporal predictor for flagging HW/CW events and as a continuous variable representing the intensity of these events. Consequently, the consortium will evaluate the ML models' performance by comparing the statistical distribution between downscaled and observational data, as well as through metrics like the F1-score and recall, which assess the model's capability to detect extreme values during HW and CW conditions.

Attention mechanisms and feature importance analysis will be integrated and reported, to enhance explainability. Despite the challenges from using Explainable AI (XAI) in geospatial artificial intelligence, several techniques can help in disclosing ML models behaviour. A non-exhaustive list of approaches to be tested in **CLIM4cities** can be seen in Table 5.

Table 5 Algorithms and approaches for XAI and their utility in spatially explicit models (adapted from Xing and Sierber 2023).

Approaches	Description	Example algorithm used for GeoAI	Source
Rule-based explanations	Embedding domain knowledge to assess the difference between given advice and a novel situation	Linear regression	Veronesi et al. (2017)
Tree-based explanations	Employing decision trees to explain how different input can be used to generate corresponding results	Classification and regression trees	Lee and Kim (2020)
Gradient-based explanations	Measuring changes from the reference towards the input along a path, for example, comparing layer to layer or neuron to layer	Integrated gradient	Luo et al. (2021)
Layer-based explanations	Attributing each neuron layer calculated from their relevance, which measures their contribution towards the generated results	Layer-wise relevance propagation (LRP)	Sonnewald and Lguensat (2021)

Feature importance is a fundamental method within XAI. This approach helps identify which input features have the most impact on the predictions of a ML model. Techniques like SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) values, which allocate importance scores to individual features, shed light on the significance of various input variables. In order to support the goals of XAI by enhancing understanding of the model's mechanics and validating its predictive power, ablation studies will be implemented (Hammed et al., 2022). These methods will be documented for the final ML models in Work Packages WP4100 ECV 1 [LST]: Algorithm Description and Validation and WP4200 ECV 2 [T2m]: Algorithm Description and Validation. We will also consider how specific weather conditions might influence model accuracy. For example, we will examine whether the significance of certain features aligns with our understanding of the UEB in influencing the UHI. This includes assessing if higher storage heat flux densities lead to increased LST and if evapotranspiration results in lower LST values. Additionally, we will evaluate how specific

weather conditions impact model performance, such as reduced accuracy during windy conditions compared to calm days. This analysis will help researchers and stakeholders identify the environmental and urban factors that most significantly affect LST variations. We will further explore pixel-wise analysis techniques to identify spatial patterns in the decisions made by the ML model (Bach et al., 2015; Cho et al., 2022).

For the temporal and spatiotemporal validations, the consortium shall use data unseen during model training and fine-tuning (also called test data, in ML/AI literature); for the validation against a reference, other sources of unbiased and quality ensured data shall be gathered. These components include the following (see Figure 7 – Diagram of the validation concept, depicting the several components: spatial, spatiotemporal, and against reference datasets.):

1. Temporal Validation: this component pertains to testing the generalisation capabilities of the ML model in time. For this temporally-unbiased validation, **CLIM4cities** will withhold a subset of the time series of data collected, including all the necessary variables to replicate the downscaling model. Out of the four years of data gathered, one will be kept solely for validation purposes, so the final ML model shall be used to generate downscaled predictions for this unbiased year. The resulting predictions shall be compared with the observational data used as the target response variable (i.e., by converting it to the native resolution of the low resolution LST, and compared) and the standard error parameters reported (e.g., MAE, RMSE). The resulting validation proves the ML model ability to generate downscaled LST imagery on the trained cities, using the same predictors, but for a temporal domain outside of the training data;
2. Spatio-temporal Validation: this component concerns the ability of the model to generalise to locations not seen during the training. Such as the case of the third city (e.g., Aalborg) where ML model downscaled predictions shall be computed and

compared against the lower resolution LST, following the same process described above. The resulting validation allows the evaluation of the ML model's performance when scaling its predictions to regions outside the training spatial domain, providing insights on its spatial scalability.

3. Validation Against Reference Data: this component is the most unbiased one, in the sense that it aims to benchmark the ML model performance against 'gold standard' datasets. Ideally, this step should be conducted using quality assured reliable data which can be assumed to be the 'ground truth' or 'gold standard'. Currently, there are very few missions providing free thermal imagery which can be used for LST validation – most commonly, Landsat 8/9 are used for downscaled LST validation, both having a sub-kilometric resolution (100m, respectively). However, considering the latitude of the case study cities, there are no ECOSTRESS scenes available. Hence, Landsat 8/9 will be the preferred choice to be used as the reference data for the *Land Surface Temperature [LST] ML model*, after conversion of its thermal infrared bands into LST (details of this preprocessing are described in WP3200 Geospatial Data Collection and Processing), hence serving as the 'true observation' to calculate the errors.

In addition, there are two aspects specific for the *T2m ML model* that should be highlighted:

1. Reference data: during the validation of our model, for each of the generalisation testing presented previously (see logic in Figure 7), the precision of the predictions will be benchmarked against three types of reference data unseen by the model: (i) in-situ observations from official stations not used in training and fine-tuning (e.g., from WMO and DMI); (ii) gridded products derived from observations, giving preference to mature observation-based gridded data, such as E-OBS daily gridded meteorological data for Europe available from Copernicus Climate Change

Service (<https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/insitu-gridded-observations-europe?tab=overview>); and (iii) reanalysis products that reconstruct historical series, giving preference to the CERRA-Land sub-daily regional reanalysis data for Europe (<https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-cerra-land?tab=overview>), available from the same source. Concerning the in-situ data, **CLIM4cities** shall collocate grid predictions with the observations contained in that grid-cell. Regarding gridded reference data, since there are spatial resolution differences, resampling of the predictions shall be performed to ensure adjustment between grids.

2. Reporting model performance during HW/CW: as described in WP4100, in this task we will also address the issue of ML model performance under extreme temperature conditions. However, in addition to the statistics described in WP4100, in WP4200 we shall also calculate the precision and recall (F1-score) of the ML model in replicating the daily mean temperature values observed in the reference data, i.e., to assess its ability in going above/below the HW/CW thresholds.

Figure 7 Diagram of the validation concept, depicting the several components: spatial, spatiotemporal, and against reference datasets.

1.2.2.4 Computational Requirements

The Python-based ML model designed for downscaling air temperatures at the metropolitan level calculates temperatures by integrating hourly-varying synoptic conditions from national weather services with local geographic and urban indicators from static geospatial and Earth Observation (EO) data. The operational ML model, encapsulated in a single Python module, will produce three types of outputs: downscaled air temperatures in NetCDF format across a regular 200x200m grid. The computational needs for this T2m model cover both data storage and processing. It requires a desktop computer with about 200 MB of storage for the twice-daily runs that generate two NetCDF files each,

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plus 13 MB for input data storage and over 6 GB for the model and its code. This setup does not use a GPU and runs on an i7-10700 processor with 8 cores and 64 GB RAM. The model, developed in Python 3.9, is compatible with Linux, Ubuntu 20.04 or newer, and utilises key libraries such as xarray, scikit-learn, matplotlib, pandas, absl-py, geopandas, earthpy, tqdm, and cdo to ensure proper functionality. For the LST model similar requirements will have to be assured.

1.2.2.5 Post-processing Requirements

In terms of data delivery, to facilitate users' interpretation of the data, a single final prediction grid shall be delivered, in 200x200m regularly spaced matrix format. In addition to the predictions of the two ECVs, i.e., T2m and LST, they will also be post-processed into statistical summaries of anomalies. The final formulation for the anomalies shall be better defined during follow-up discussions, but as of now, the following alternatives are being considered:

- UHI intensity: daily T2m diurnal and nocturnal differences between the city-centre daily maximum (day) and minimum (night) temperatures compared to non-urban surrounding.
- SUHI intensity: weekly LST diurnal and nocturnal differences between the city-centre weekly maximum (day) and minimum (night) temperatures compared to non-urban surrounding.
- T2m anomaly: daily T2m diurnal and nocturnal differences compared to long-term reference climatology (e.g., from ERA5).
- LST anomaly: weekly LST diurnal and nocturnal differences compared to long-term reference averages (e.g., from ESA-CCI).
- T2m heat/cold anomaly (i.e., hot days and tropical nights indices): daily T2m diurnal and nocturnal differences compared to long-term reference 90/10 percentiles (e.g., from E-OBS or ERA5).

- LST heat/cold anomaly: weekly LST diurnal and nocturnal differences compared to long-term reference 90/10 percentiles (e.g., from ESA-CCI).
- Excess Heat/Cold Factor: daily mean T2m-based indices of heat/cold intensities, based on long-term percentiles (e.g., from E-OBS or ERA5).

Alternative metrics might be considered, as a function of users' priorities and feasibility in the scope of the project.

1.3 EO Use Case Definition and ECV Description [LST and T2m] [WP1300]

1.3.1 Consolidation of Danish Users Needs

Based on the workshops and dialogues with Danish stakeholders a number of overarching user needs have been identified:

- **Resolution:** The T2m/UHI data and LST/SUHI products can be adopted and worked with in as high resolution as can be provided. Generally, professional Danish users wish for a data product that could be used to identify the effect of individual buildings, and their composition of materials, on the UHI, as most other planning data in Denmark is at similar high resolution.
- **Data format:** The main recipients for the initial UHI/SUHI datasets are the planning bodies of the municipalities, as they work with GIS data. Hence, the UHI maps should be provided in an open GIS-format, and ideally through a web-GIS interface or other sources where it can easily plug into existing workflows.
- **ML model:** The model should be documented to a degree so end users can pick it up and use it for scenario analyses afterwards. This also requires that the UHI/SUHI model results reported within **CLIM4cities** can be related back to the different input influence groups: regional, landscape and urban, with a special focus on the urban

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area where the small scale differences constitute the input variables where urban development scenarios can be formulated and tested.

- **Coverage:** For now, the project covers the four largest cities in Denmark. There is a clear demand for an assessment of how small cities can be expected to have an UHI effect and thus, a wish for a data product that covers more and smaller cities than the ones included. This is beyond the **CLIM4cities** project, but points towards a need for immediate further work that DMI should conduct in direct response to the project: Performing the analysis on Danish cities on decreasing sizes in order to determine the minimum size a city should have in order to have an expected UHI effect.

Besides these needs, there have been numerous expressed needs for products that can utilise the results of **CLIM4Cities**, but these will have to rely on further development that is beyond the project. In short, these are: operational UHI warning systems, development of health related indicators where the T2m/LST and/or UHI/SUHI maps are combined with other environmental and socioeconomic drivers, mitigation scenarios and a mitigation strategy database. These will be discussed further with the relevant stakeholders, and where relevant ideas will be matured.

1.3.2 Definition of Areas of Interest, Climate and Urban Characterisation

Denmark boasts an extensive coastline spanning a remarkable 7,300 km. Notably, around 40% of Denmark's population resides within a mere 3 km of this captivating coast (Sørensen, 2013). This coastal expanse encompasses a blend of urban areas, holiday homes, recreational spaces, and substantial stretches of unspoiled natural beauty.

In accordance with the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change's (IPCC) fourth assessment report (IPCC, 2023), Denmark is poised to undergo notable climate changes.

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These changes include a generally warmer climate featuring milder, wetter winters and hotter, drier summers. Expectations include an overall increase in annual precipitation, although summers may witness reduced rainfall. This shift in precipitation patterns is expected to give rise to both drought periods and more intense rainfall events (Sørup et al., 2017, 2016). Additionally, there is a growing risk of extreme weather events, including prolonged HW and more severe storms (Lind et al., 2020).

In a significant study conducted by (Alexander, 2021), the impact of vegetation proportions, building heights, and proximity on urban land surface temperatures was meticulously examined. The study's geographic scope encompassed four of Denmark's largest cities: Copenhagen, Aarhus, Odense, and Aalborg. These urban centres are characterised by a substantial urban population of 87.7% and exhibit distinct climate profiles.

The climate in Denmark is relatively warm compared to its northern location underlining the strong influence from the ocean and in particular the Gulf Stream on the local climate. This is expressed in a Dfb classification of temperate climate, as 'no dry season but warm summers' (Alexander, 2021; Beck et al., 2018). Temperatures are most influenced by the ocean along the coast, with a slightly smaller influence in the middle of Jutland furthest from the coast. Rainfall varies from approximately 500 to 1000 mm/year with a pronounced East–West gradient. There are no significant regional differences with respect to number or length of dry periods or other heat related indices.

Figure 8 Locations and land surface temperature (LST) measurement based on Landsat 8 imagery for the four cities of interest. Figure reproduced from (Alexander, 2021).

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Figure 9 Map of the build-up areas within the Greater Copenhagen area with municipal borders. From <https://kamp.klimatilpasning.dk/>.

Figure 8 shows the LST measurements for selected days based on Landsat 8 imagery as presented in (Alexander, 2021). The Copenhagen area is restricted to cover only Copenhagen and Frederiksberg municipalities, while the connected built up urban area is larger, spanning far out into the surrounding municipalities. Even so, the only large connected green area of Copenhagen Municipality is cropped from the picture. The contrary situation is the case for the other cities; here only the urban centres of the single municipalities corresponding to the cities investigated are covered, and the images are

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cropped to leave out surrounding rural and green areas. As such, the Greater Copenhagen area covers a much larger connected urban area than any of the other cities, and from an administrative point of view a much more diverse landscape with a connected urban coverage spanning more than 10 municipalities, see Figure 9, compared to e.g. Aarhus where the whole urban area is isolated to one municipality, see Figure 10.

Figure 10 Map of the build-up areas within the city of Aarhus with municipal borders. From <https://kamp.klimatilpasning.dk/>.

In Copenhagen, the Municipality of Copenhagen points towards pluvial and coastal flooding as the primary climate challenge, but UHI and related problems are also seen as a serious challenge (Copenhagen Municipality, 2011). For the Municipality of Frederiksberg, who does

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not have coastline, pluvial flooding and UHI are both seen as very important climate challenges, but flooding is seen as a problem already relevant today, and UHI is regarded as a challenge for the future when the climate in Denmark gets warmer (Frederiksberg Municipality, 2021).

In the current climate adaptation plans for Aarhus and Aalborg, extreme heat or UHI is not at all recognized as a potential problem (Aalborg Municipality, 2014; Aarhus Municipality, 2013), whereas, increases in HWs is mentioned in Odense's plan, but UHI is not (Odense Municipality, 2022). However, from the discussions with the Municipality of Aarhus it is evident that they are currently working on updating their climate adaptation plan, where UHI is recognized as an important topic there.

In Figure 8, it is clear that at least the LST shows some distinct urban patterns, with increased values in areas with denser building mass. It is likely that all three cities will experience a recognisable UHI already under the current climate, and that the effect will be stronger in the future climate.

The development plans for all four cities point to the same tendencies (Aalborg Municipality, 2024; Aarhus Municipality, 2024; Copenhagen Municipality, 2024; Odense Municipality, 2022):

- The number of inhabitants are increasing, coinciding with an increasing demand for housing and workplaces. This trend is expected to continue in the foreseeable future.
- This increase is accommodated through a general densification of existing urban areas and, for the cities outside of Copenhagen that have rural areas available, also through urban sprawl in these areas. As such, the built-up urban area is expected to increase and densify across all areas of interest. Urban sprawl is happening in the Greater Copenhagen Area, much further away from the urban centre and in surrounding municipalities.

- Furthermore, all cities have focused on increased connected natural areas within the cities, as well as Nature-Based Solutions and Blue-Green Infrastructure in relation to management of hydro-climatic extremes (Viti et al., 2023). In that relation, a focus on mitigation possibilities for other types of climate effects, such as UHI, is also touched upon, but is less explicitly included than water-related issues.

1.3.3 Target Key Performance Indicators (KPI's) for the Machine Learning Models

The KPIs for the ML model outputs must be precisely defined to meet the requirements of end-users. This includes spatial scale and coverage, granularity, time-period inclusion, output formats, variables, and geographic projection. Compliance with CF-compliant netCDF format ensures unambiguous and interoperable data representation, facilitating seamless integration with existing systems and workflows. To ensure the twinning strategy between both the T2m and LST downscaling models, which is desirable from a user perspective, a single target grid of regularly-spaced 200x200m shall be used. In each case, the final outputs shall be resamples for this grid for user data supply purposes (i.e., to integrate on existing platforms, as needed). Table 6 to Table 8, show examples of outputs of existing models developed in Oliveira et al. (2021) and Oliveira et al. (2022) as well as expected and to aim for KPIs on **CLIM4Cities**.

Table 6 Example of Data Description from a pilot ML model output for Land Surface Temperature (LST) in Naples (Oliveira et al, 2022; Oliveira et al, 2021) and targeted CLIM4Cities KPIs

DATA DESCRIPTION		
	Existing Model	Target KPIs
Data type	Gridded	Gridded
Projection	Regular latitude–longitude grid	Regular latitude–longitude grid
Horizontal coverage	Naples Functional Urban Area, as per Urban Atlas Boundary (Copernicus Land Monitoring Service, 2006)	Danish Aol's (several) Functional Urban Area, as per Urban Atlas Boundary (Copernicus Land Monitoring Service, 2006)
Horizontal resolution	100 x 100 m	200mx200m
Vertical coverage	Surface Skin	Surface Skin
Vertical resolution	Single level	Single level
Temporal coverage	Single day	Single day
Temporal resolution	Day Scene Night Scene	Diurnal Mean Nocturnal Mean
File format	GeoTIFF	GeoTIFF
Update frequency	N.a. (single scene–based model)	Weekly or Monthly (depending on cloud cover, either is enough according to user requirements)
Variable	Land Surface (Skin) Temperature	Land Surface (Skin) Temperature
Units	Kelvin	Kelvin
Uncertainty MAE	MAE inferior to 0.1°K, adjusted R2 = 0.948, p-value < 0.001 (against test observations)	MAE inferior to 0.1°K, adjusted R2 = 0.90, p-value < 0.001 (against test observations)
WMO ECV compliance (GCOS, 2022)	Compliant with Horizontal and Vertical Resolutions, Measurement Uncertainty (2–sigma). Compliance with the Timeliness requirement is not applicable to a single scene–based model and can only be confirmed upon applying it to a time series of data, as foreseen in CLIM4cities . Stability is not applicable.	

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Table 7 Example of Data Description from a pilot ML model output for near surface Air Temperature (T2m) in Lisbon (Oliveira et al., 2022; Oliveira et al., 2021) and targeted CLIM4Cities

DATA DESCRIPTION		
	Existing Model	Target KPIs
Data type	Gridded	Gridded
Projection	Regular latitude–longitude grid	Regular latitude–longitude grid
Horizontal coverage	Lisbon Functional Urban Area, as per Urban Atlas Boundary (Copernicus Land Monitoring Service, 2006)	Danish Aols (several) Functional Urban Area, as per Urban Atlas Boundary (Copernicus Land Monitoring Service, 2018)
Horizontal resolution	250 x 250 m	200 x 200 m
Vertical coverage	Surface	Surface
Vertical resolution	Single level	Single level
Temporal coverage	From 2022 until the present (operational version)	From 2020 until the present (2023 for unbiased validation)
Temporal resolution	Hourly (48h forecast, based on AROME–Iberian Peninsula) (IPMA, 2023)	hourly (18h forecast, based on AROME–NEA domain) (DMI, 2023)
File format	NetCDF	NetCDF
Update frequency	Twice Daily (12:00 and 24:00 runs)	Eight times Daily (03:00, 06:00 etc.)
Variable	Surface (Air) Temperature	Surface (Air) Temperature
Units	°C	°C
Uncertainty MAE	MAE: 1.46°C, adjusted R2 = 0.941, p–value < 0.001 (against reference WMO observations)	MAE: 1.5°C, adjusted R2 = 0.90, p–value < 0.001 (against reference WMO observations)
WMO ECV compliance (GCOS, 2022)	Compliant with Horizontal and Temporal Resolutions and Timeliness. Measurement Uncertainty (2–sigma) not compliant (<1°K) but reduced from 3.64°C (AROME against WMO observations) to 1.56°C (model against WMO observations). Stability not applicable.	Compliant with Horizontal and Temporal Resolutions and Timeliness. Measurement Uncertainty (2–sigma) compliance as close as possible to ECV standards (i.e., <1°K). Stability not applicable.

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Table 8 Example of data description from a pilot ML model output for near surface Air Temperature (T2m) according to different climatic scenarios (Oliveira et al., 2021) and targeted CLIM4Cities KPIs

DATA DESCRIPTION		
	Existing Model	Target KPIs
Data type	Gridded	Gridded
Projection	Regular latitude–longitude grid	Regular latitude–longitude grid
Horizontal coverage	Lisbon Functional Urban Area, as per Urban Atlas Boundary (Copernicus Land Monitoring Service, 2006)	Danish Aols (several) Functional Urban Area, as per Urban Atlas Boundary (Copernicus Land Monitoring Service, 2018)
Horizontal resolution	250 x 250 m	200 x 200 m
Vertical coverage	Surface	Surface
Vertical resolution	Single level	Single level
Temporal coverage	2081–2100, 95th percentile, with RCP8.5 scenario, as per (Parente et al., 2018), i.e., 6.9 °C above the 90th percentile in the Lisbon	DestinE Climate Scenarios: Standard resolution Climate DT on single levels – SSP3–7.0 – IFS–NEMO 0001
Temporal resolution	Daily	Daily
File format	NetCDF	NetCDF
Update frequency	n.a.	n.a.
Variable	Surface (Air) Temperature	Surface (Air) Temperature
Units	°C	°C
Uncertainty MAE	n.a.	n.a.
WMO ECV compliance (GCOS, 2022)	Compliant with Horizontal and Temporal Resolutions and Timeliness. Measurement Uncertainty (2–sigma) not calculated.	Compliant with Horizontal and Temporal Resolutions and Timeliness. Measurement Uncertainty (2–sigma) not calculated.

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2 Summary and Outlook

Over the past two decades, UHI has developed from a niche to a widespread topic within research as a result of cities and people experiencing the effect in many places around the world. It is not a theoretical problem connected to future climate change; it is a severe phenomenon already evident with the changes to the climate we experience now. As a consequence, methods to best possibly establish the UHI are being developed and, given the spatial complexity of UHI, data needs are high. Here Earth Observations (EO) data is extremely valuable, especially when used with other sources of data. The State-of-the-Art analysis showcases how the understanding of UHI is very mature, and how it links back to the urban morphology and e.g. building stocks. It also showcases why most existing traditional ground-based datasets lack the ability to properly inform UHI models.

The Gap Analysis points to a huge potential in combining EO data with local crowdsourced citizen-owned weather station data, as these, in contrast to weather stations operated by meteorological services, usually aren't installed in a way to minimise the urban impacts; In Copenhagen, meteorological stations are in general installed in green areas explicitly to avoid measurements of the urban "bias", i.e. the UHI effect. The analysis shows that there is ambient data available from such local weather stations, and the scientific challenges in using them lies mainly within quality assurance, as they are not placed according to any standards. Moreover, data availability, as they are privately owned and crowdsourced through private companies.

The spatial complexity of UHI also raises flags in the Gap Analysis. Even the processes leading to UHI that are understood are extremely difficult to model at the relevant scales due to large computational needs and input data. Additionally, further adding the less understood process makes physically based dynamical downscaling infeasible. Here, ML and AI are attractive approaches to pursue in order to have more computational efficient models to describe the highly complex relationships behind UHI. These still have a high

demand for input data and must be developed consciously in order to avoid problems like overfitting, but the potential benefit is huge.

Urban climate services based on EO data, numerical weather prediction model and climate model output data and local observations are far from the norm. All data sources have information of relevance, but their integration is seemingly difficult, although necessary in order to produce UHI products at scales of relevance that can be used both for current conditions as well as for future climatic conditions.

The direct engagement with Danish stakeholders has shown that there exists a demand for detailed UHI products and that the work with UHI is just starting in the Danish context. This demand is for high resolution maps and operational warning products, as well as for scenario models that can help decision making in relation to mitigation efforts. While high resolution maps are absolutely within the scope of this project, scenario models could be a further development to the models developed within this project; thus, it requires that these models are well structured and documented.

The Requirement Analysis shows that it is technically possible to develop models that meet the user requirements and outlines the scientific challenges that have to be overcome in order to do so. These challenges primarily revolve around input data constraints, methodological uncertainties, and technical limitations. Satellite imagery, while available year-round, presents issues related to spatial resolution, granularity, and cloud cover, impacting remote-sensing-based processing and data reconstruction and validation. Furthermore, synchronous direct measurements of atmospheric parameters are typically scarce, complicating the validation process. The reliance on descriptive numerical models is hampered by knowledge gaps in understanding complex Earth systems interactions, including those involving the hydrosphere, atmosphere, and biosphere. Finally, aligning spatial resolutions of different datasets, requires re-projection to ensure uniform resolution. The use of ML and AI modelling approaches introduces uncertainties,

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particularly due to the reliance on consistent input datasets for accurate results. Achieving this consistency can be challenging before the data acquisition stage. Additionally, ML models can only predict outcomes based on patterns present in the training dataset, and in contexts where feature relationships differ, the results may not align with expectations. To address these, the consortium will use alternative datasets, data fusion techniques, and a multidisciplinary approach for robust data collection and integration. Methodological uncertainties and technical constraints also pose significant challenges. Consistent input datasets and the context sensitivity of ML models requires an iterative process for data handling, model training, and testing to optimise inputs and parameters. Additionally, the computational demands of the data and infrastructure configuration challenges will be managed through clear data handling procedures and adequate computational resources.

This matches well with the intended areas under study (the four largest cities in Denmark), and the analysis shows that significantly different climatic conditions between the cities are not expected. As such, the developed models are expected to be easily transferable between locations and the selected Key Performance Indicators to be realistic. To meet end-user requirements, the KPIs for the ML model outputs were defined in terms of spatial scale and coverage, granularity, time-period inclusion, output formats, variables, and geographic projection. Ensuring compliance with CF-compliant netCDF format will facilitate seamless integration with existing systems and workflows. Finally, a single target grid of regularly spaced 200x200 metres will be used to ensure consistency between T2m and LST models.

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